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Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW FREQUENCY OF GYNECOLOGICAL
MALIGNANCIES TREATMENT IN A TERTIARY CARE
HOSPITAL**

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¹Punjab Medical College Faislabad²Foundation university Medical college Islamabad³Foundation University Medical college Islamabad**Abstract:****Objective:** The objective of the article is to determine the frequency of different genital tract malignancies.**Study Design:** Descriptive / cross-sectional study**Place and Duration of Study:** This study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Allied Hospital Faislabad from Jan 2016 to March 2017.**Materials and Methods:** All the patients with genital tract malignancies confirmed by the Histopathology report were included. Relevant data and history was obtained and physical examination and investigations were done in all the patients. Specimens were sent for histopathology. Clinical & surgical staging was done according to the FIGO classification.**Results:** 105 patients with gynecological malignancies were included in the study. The most common (42%) Carcinoma of the ovary, second most common Cervical Cancer (25%) and Uterine Cancer (17%). Choriocarcinoma was found in (7.6%) patients and vulvae & vaginal cancer was found in (6.6%) with the mean age of 50 years. The lowest parity in ovarian cancers was (21%) and cervical & uterine cancers were (31%). Ovarian cancers (34%) and abdominal pain (24%). Weight loss was evident in (25%) & anorexia in (20%). Uterine & cervical cancers with irregular vaginal bleeding (24%) and postmenopausal bleeding (16%), vaginal discharge (16%). 65% patient were in stage iii & iv. The Serous most common was cystadenocarcinoma commonest ovarian malignancy (40%), while most common cervical cancer was squamous cell carcinoma (85%) & endometroid endometrial carcinoma (55%) the most common was uterine carcinoma.**Conclusion:** In this study major gynaecological malignancy was Ovarian Cancer in advanced stages. Patient education is essential for early diagnosis and treatment of ovarian cancer.**Corresponding author:**Dr.Kiran Yasmeen Malik,
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INTRODUCTION:

Cancer is an abnormal proliferation of cells of the body and it is a challenging health problem around the globe. A study on global cancer statistics by the international agency for research on cancer indicates that this type of cancer accounts for 5.1 million estimated new cases, 2.9 million cancer deaths and 13 million [5 years] prevalent cancer cases among women in the world [1].

It is the most common form of cancer in women in developing countries and third most common worldwide. The current coverage for Cervical Cancer Screening in Pakistan is as low as 1.9% and that is one of the reasons of growing cervical cancer [2]. In 2008 according to GLOBOCAN (World Health Organization Project for Cancer research in Pakistan) incidence of cervical cancer is 19.6%/100,000 as compared to less than 9.1/100,000 in 2002. Data on screening in the past 5 years for Cervical Dysplasia coverage in developed countries is 85% whereas for under developed is 5% [3]. Cervical cancer in developed countries has come down due to wide coverage of cervical screening [1,4].

Ovary Cancer causes most deaths than any other cancer in females globally. An overall 5 years rate of survival is only 30% in the United Kingdom [5]. It can occur at any age but most common after menopause. More than 60% women are diagnosed with cancer in stage III and stage IV disease [6]. Prognosis of the cancer is stage dependent 92% at stage I & 5% at stage IV. The overall 5 year survival rate is 70%. In order to reduce morbidity and mortality from gynaecological cancers, strategies are needed to be devised for better screening, diagnosis and management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was cross sectional and descriptive. The study was conducted at Allied Hospital Faisalabad from JAN 2016 to March 2017, All patients having benign tumors were not included in the study and relevant data regarding age, symptoms, examination, investigations, surgical procedures and staging (clinical and surgical) was according to FIGO classification of tumors. Different histopathological types of cancer were entered on a predesigned questionnaire.

RESULTS:

105 cases of gynecological malignancies were reported and treated in our center. The frequency of gynecological malignancies was recorded 2% and ovarian cancer was most common, in (42%) women, second most was cervical cancer found in (25%) patients, endometrial cancer [17%], choriocarcinoma in 8 [7.6%] and 7 cases of vulval and vaginal cancer (6.6%).

The mean age of the patients was recorded 50 years. The highest number of gynecological malignancies occurred between 50-60years. The highest parity was seen in uterine and cervical cancer (31%) and the lowest in ovarian cancer (21%). Vulval and Choriocarcinoma were also seen in parous patients.

Ovarian malignancies with abdominal mass were found in (34%) patients, patients with abdominal pain were (24%), weight loss (25%) and anorexia (20%). Uterine & cervical malignancies commonly presented with post-menopausal bleeding (16%) & irregular vaginal bleeding (24%) & discharge (16%). Vulval ulcer and swelling (3%).

Figure No.1: Frequency of Gynaecological Malignancies

Table No.1: Age of Distribution of Gynaecological Malignancies

Age Range (years)	Uterus N=18	Ovary N=45	Cervix 27=n	Vulva 7=n	Chorio- carcinoma N=8	%age N=105
Less than 40	-	16	-	1	4	20%
40-49	2	9	5	2	3	20%
50-59	6	10	11	1	1	27.6%
60 and above	10	10	11	3	-	32%

Among the patients with malignancies 68/105 (64%) cases at stage III & IV.

Table No.2: The stage of presentation of different gynecological malignancies

Stage	Ovarian	Uterine	Cervical	Vulval	%age
Borderlin	4	-	-	-	3.8%
Stage 1	-	4	1	-	4.7%%
Stage 2	5	9	3	3	19%
Stage 3	19	3	12	1	33%
Stage 4	17	2	11	3	31%

Table No.3: Distribution of parity among the subjects with gynaecological malignancies

Diagnosis	Para 0	Para 1	Para 2-4	Para >5	%age
Uterine cancer	1	-	2	15	17%
Cervical cancer	3	-	6	18	25%
Ovarian cancer	18	5	10	12	42%
Vulval/ vaginal cancer	3	-	1	3	6.6%
Choriocar- cinoma		1	2	5	7.6%

Table No.4: Clinical presentation of different gynecological malignancies

Presenting Symptoms	Ovarian	uterine	Cervical	Vulval	Choriocarcinoma	Percentage
Irregular bleeding	2	5	12	1	8	24%
PMB	3	8	8	-	-	16%
PCB	-	-	6	-	-	5%
Vaginal discharge/Itching	-	3	8	2	-	16%
Abdominal Mass	32	3	-	-	4	34%
Abdominal Pain	18	2	6	-	2	24%
Ulcer / swelling	-	-	-	4	-	3%
Weight loss	20	-	7	-	-	25%
Dyspareunia	-	-	8	-	3	10%
Anorexia	15	-	6	-	3	20%

Table No.5: Histopathological type of gynecological malignancies

Histopathological types	Ovarian	Uterine	Cervical	Vulval	Percentage
Serous cyst adenocarcinoma	18				40%
Mucinous cyst adenocarcinoma	7				15.5%
Papillary cell adenocarcinoma	2				4%
Dysgerminoma	6				13.3%
Sertoli Leydig cell tumor	1				2%
Endometrioid carcinoma	1	10			55%
Granulosa cell tumor	2				4.4%
Squamous cell carcinoma			23	5	85.2%
Struma ovarii	1				2%
Adenocarcinoma			2	2	8.8%
Adenosquamous carcinoma			2		7.4%
Immature Teratoma	3				6.6%
Germ cell tumor	3				6.6%
Carcinosarcoma		1			5.5%
Borderline tumor	4				8.8%
Choriocarcinoma	1	8			16%
Leiomyosarcoma		1			5.5%
Invasive mole		1			3.5%

DISCUSSION:

Gynecological malignancy varies in different geographical areas. The frequency of gynecological malignancies is 2%, which is related to a report by Ashraf T (1.8%) but is slightly higher in comparison to 0.32% by Mohyuddin et al and 0.92% by Akhtar et al [7-9]. However, reported a high incidence of (10%) in Nigeria with majority of patients having cervical cancer [19].

In this study found to be most common gynecological malignancy (42%) was ovarian cancer, followed by cervical cancer (25%) and endometrial cancer (17%), as observed in other studies^{11,12, 15}.

International studies show that cervical cancer is the most common type of cancer found in women around the world [4,5,10,14]. This difference is due to Islamic State of Pakistan where extra marital sexual relation is not common. Epithelial Ovarian cancer was most common between post-menopause in women whereas germ cell tumors were commonality in children and adolescents. This associates with some national and international studies [7,9,13,16]. Ovarian Cancer is common in nulliparous women, ovarian carcinoma with abdominal mass, abdominal pain, weight loss and anorexia, that is similar to the results reported by Junejo et al¹⁶. Surface epithelial tumor forms main histopathological group in this study, correlated with other

national and international studies⁸ [8,9,12,15]. The epithelial ovarian cancer Serous cyst adenocarcinoma was common type of cancer (40%), mucinous cyst adenocarcinoma being the second most common (13%) whereas Ahmed et al found mucinous cyst adenocarcinoma as the most common variety [13].

This study reveals that cervical cancer was the second most common in gynecological malignancies correlates to other national studies. [7,8,10,12] While studies from other developing countries like Bangladesh, India and Africa shows cervical cancer occupied the top most position [2,4,10,15]. The highest point of cervical cancer in this study was between 50-70 years of age, which coincide with results reported by similar national studies [9,11]. The Squamous cell carcinoma (85%) was the most common cervical cancer in this study, followed by adenocarcinoma (8.8%) which is similar to other studies [2,10,11,17,15]

The third common malignancy was endometrial cancer in our study, that correlates with other studies [1,7,15,16,17]. Comparatively the incidence rate of this malignancy is less in Asia and Africa than that of developed western countries [1,7,8,15]. The main histopathological type of endometrial cancer was endometrioid carcinoma (55%). Percentage of choriocarcinoma in this study is 7.6%, which correlates with other studies [7,20]. In this study 2/3rd of genital tract malignancies diagnosed at stage III and IV, except endometrial carcinoma which was presented in early stages. Late

diagnosis poses surgical challenge and results in poor treatment outcome. In fact, 16% cases in this study were inoperable at the time of diagnosis.

This study finds ovarian tumours as the major type of gynaecological malignancy. Better awareness of the symptoms of ovarian cancer may lead to earlier diagnosis and treatment and thus be the reason to improved prognosis.

CONCLUSION:

Screening, regular examination and well executed follow up can change the morbidity and mortality rate.

Education is essential for early diagnosis and treatment which would improve the survival rate. Every patient with Cancer requires proper clinical diagnosis and evaluation, surgery and optimal therapy.

Conflict of Interest: The study has no conflict of interest to declare by any author.

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